

CHEMISTRY OF AMINOBENZOTHAZOLES: SOME RELATED THIO-CARBAMIDES, CARBAMIDES, CARBODI-IMIDES AND GUANIDINES

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Several derivatives of thiocarbamide, carbamide, carbodi-imide, and guanidine containing a substituted or unsubstituted 2-aminobenzothiazole group are described.

During the course of an investigation of the chemistry of certain heterocyclic bases, derived from aromatic thiocarbamides, it became necessary to synthesise thiocarbamides, carbamides, guanidines, and carbodi-imides related to 2-aminobenzothiazole. Except for *N*-2-benzothiazolyl-*N'*-phenylthiocarbamide (I) and the related urea (Kaufmann, G.P., 560, 944/1930), 2-benzothiazolylguanidine (II) (Smith *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 53, 4103; Niino, *J. Pharm. Soc. Japan*, 1953, 63, 249), and some of its other derivatives of which no preparatory details have been published (Roy *et al.*, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1955, 14B, 474), no other compounds of the above categories appear to have been prepared.

[R=H or an aryl group]

A number of *N*-2-benzothiazolyl-*N'*-arylthiocarbamides of the type (I) have now been prepared by the condensation of the desired 2-aminobenzothiazole with the appropriate aryl isothiocyanate (Table I). These on treatment with yellow lead oxide in benzene afforded the related carbodi-imides (III) (Table II), which on hydrolysis formed the corresponding carbamides (IV) (Table III). The same carbamides have also been prepared by alternative routes, thus confirming the identity of the carbodi-imides.

The *N*-2-benzothiazolyl-*N'*-arylthiocarbamides (I) in presence of lead oxide condensed with ammonia in a sealed tube to afford the related guanidines [cf. (II), Table IV]; their hydrochlorides and picrates were prepared and the equivalent weight of the former was determined.

EXPERIMENTAL

N-Aryl-*N'*-2-benzothiazolylthiocarbamides

(i). Phenyl-, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-tolyl-, and *p*-phenetyl-thiocarbamides were prepared by boiling the respective amine thiocyanates, obtained in solution by mixing an aqueous solution of amine hydrochloride and ammonium thiocyanate (this *Journal*, 1935, 12, 629). These thiocarbamides on their oxidation with bromine in inert solvents like benzene or chloroform gave the 2-aminobenzothiazole and 4-methyl-, 5-methyl-, 6-methyl-, and 6-ethoxy- 2-aminobenzothiazole respectively (Hunter, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 2023, 2270; 1926, 1385; Kaufmann, *Arch. Pharm.*, 1928, 256, 197).

(ii). Phenyl, *o*-, *m*-, and *p*-tolyl isothiocyanates were prepared from the ammonium salt of the corresponding dithiocarbamate by the action of lead nitrate (Vogel, "A Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry", 1954, p. 615).

The benzothiazoles, described under (i) above, when mixed with equimolecular quantities of the appropriate isothiocyanate, described under (ii), and heated on a water bath for 3-4 hours, afforded the relative *N*-2-benzothiazolyl-*N'*-arylthiocarbamides in about 90% yield. The crude product was washed with ether, and then with HCl (dil.) to remove unchanged isothiocyanate and 2-aminobenzothiazoles. The thiocarbamides were crystallised from chlorobenzene in shining crystals. Preparations, m.p. and analyses of the compounds are summarised in Table I.

TABLE I

Reactants.	Thiocarbamide.	M.P.	Found.	Calc.
2-Amino-4-methyl-B + <i>o</i> -tolyl I.	<i>N</i> - <i>o</i> -Tolyl- <i>N'</i> -2-(4-methyl)-BT (C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₂ S ₂)	184°	C: 60.7% H: 4.7 N: 13.3 S: 20.7	61.3% 4.8 13.4 20.4
2-Amino-B + phenyl I.	<i>N</i> -Phenyl- <i>N'</i> -2-BT (C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₂ S ₂)	201°	N: 14.3 S: 22.1	14.7 22.4
2-Amino-5-methyl-B + <i>m</i> -tolyl I.	<i>N</i> - <i>m</i> -Tolyl- <i>N'</i> -2-(5-methyl)-BT (C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₂ S ₂)	188°	N: 13.2 S: 20.0	13.4 20.4
2-Amino-6-methyl-B + <i>p</i> -tolyl I.	<i>N</i> - <i>p</i> -Tolyl- <i>N'</i> -2-(6-methyl)-BT (C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₂ S ₂)	202°	N: 13.5	13.4
2-Amino-6-ethoxy-B + <i>p</i> -phenetyl I.	<i>N</i> - <i>p</i> -Phenetyl- <i>N'</i> -2-(6-ethoxy)-BT (C ₁₈ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₂ S ₂)	168°	N: 11.2	11.3
2-Amino-4-methyl-B + phenyl I.	<i>N</i> -Phenyl- <i>N'</i> -2-(4-methyl)-BT (C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₂ S ₂)	185°	N: 14.2	14.0
2-Amino-5-methyl-B + phenyl I.	<i>N</i> -Phenyl- <i>N'</i> -2-(5-methyl)-BT (C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₂ S ₂)	178°	N: 14.0	14.0
2-Amino-6-methyl-B + phenyl I.	<i>N</i> -Phenyl- <i>N'</i> -2-(6-methyl)-BT (C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₂ S ₂)	201°	N: 13.9	14.0
2-Amino-6-ethoxy-B + phenyl I.	<i>N</i> -Phenyl- <i>N'</i> -2-(6-ethoxy)-BT (C ₁₈ H ₁₉ ON ₂ S ₂)	167°	N: 12.5	12.8

BT represents benzothiazolyl thiocarbamide.

B .. benzothiazole.
I .. isothiocyanate.

N-Aryl-N'-2-benzothiazolylcarbodi-imides

A mixture of finely powdered *N*-aryl-*N'*-2-benzothiazolylthiocarbamide (2 g.) and yellow lead oxide (3 g.) was suspended in benzene (50 c.c.) and heated under reflux for about 6-8 hours. Desulphurisation was complete when no blackening occurred on addition of a further small quantity of lead oxide. The reaction mixture was then filtered hot. The filtrate on keeping deposited beautiful, light bluish yellow crystals of the carbodi-imides. These could be recrystallised from benzene and ethanol. M.p.'s and analyses of the compounds are described in Table II.

TABLE II

Thiocarbamide desulphided.	Carbodi-imide.	M.P.	Found.	Calc.
<i>N</i> -Phenyl- <i>N'</i> -2-BT	<i>N</i> -Phenyl- <i>N'</i> -2-BD (C ₁₄ H ₈ N ₂ S)	217°	C: 66.8% H: 3.9 N: 16.7 S: 12.5	66.9% 3.6 16.7 12.7
<i>N</i> - <i>o</i> -Tolyl- <i>N'</i> -2-(4-methyl)-BT	<i>N</i> - <i>o</i> -Tolyl- <i>N'</i> -2-(4-methyl)- BD (C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₂ S)	185°	C: 68.8 H: 4.7 N: 15.1 S: 11.9	68.8 4.7 15.0 11.8
<i>N</i> - <i>m</i> -Tolyl- <i>N'</i> -2-(5-methyl)-BT	<i>N</i> - <i>m</i> -Tolyl- <i>N'</i> -2-(5-methyl)- BD (C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₂ S)	224°	N: 15.4	15.0
<i>N</i> - <i>p</i> -Tolyl- <i>N'</i> -2-(6-methyl)-BT	<i>N</i> - <i>p</i> -Tolyl- <i>N'</i> -2-(6-methyl)- BD (C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₂ S)	199°	N: 15.1	15.0
<i>N</i> - <i>p</i> -Phenetyl- <i>N'</i> -2-(6-ethoxy)-BT	<i>N</i> - <i>p</i> -Phenetyl- <i>N'</i> -2-(6-ethoxy)- BD (C ₁₈ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₂ S)	110°	N: 12.1	12.4
Phenyl- <i>N'</i> -2-(4-methyl)-BT	<i>N</i> -Phenyl- <i>N'</i> -2-(4-methyl)- BD (C ₁₃ H ₁₁ N ₂ S)	167°	N: 15.5	15.8
<i>N</i> -Phenyl- <i>N'</i> -2-(5-methyl)-BT	<i>N</i> -Phenyl- <i>N'</i> -2-(5-methyl)- BD (C ₁₅ H ₁₁ N ₂ S)	214°	N: 16.2	15.8
<i>N</i> -Phenyl- <i>N'</i> -2-(6-methyl)-BT	<i>N</i> -Phenyl- <i>N'</i> -2-(6-methyl)- BD (C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₂ S)	210°	N: 16.0	15.8
<i>N</i> -Phenyl- <i>N'</i> -2-(6-ethoxy)-BT	<i>N</i> -Phenyl- <i>N'</i> -2-(6-ethoxy)- BD (C ₁₈ H ₁₅ ON ₂ S)	189°	N: 14.1	14.2

BT represents benzothiazolylthiocarbamide.

BD .. benzothiazolylcarbodi-imide

N-Aryl-N'-2-benzothiazolylcarbamides

The carbodi-imides, recorded in Table II (1 g. each), were boiled with HCl (conc., 50 c.c.). First the carbodi-imide dissolved forming a yellow solution, which on continued boiling with fresh additions of HCl became colorless and deposited a light crystalline mass of the related carbamide. It was filtered and recrystallised from chlorobenzene and glacial acetic acid. *Results are presented in Table III.

TABLE III

Carbodi-imide hydrolysed.	Carbamide formed.	*M.P.	Carbamide obtained from.	*M.P.	*Mixed M.P.
<i>N</i> -Phenyl- <i>N'</i> -2-BD	<i>N</i> -Phenyl- <i>N'</i> -2-BC (C ₁₄ H ₁₁ ON ₂ S)	298°	P+2-amino-B	300°	299°
<i>N</i> -Phenyl- <i>N'</i> -2-(4-methyl)-BD	<i>N</i> -Phenyl- <i>N'</i> -2-(4-methyl)-BC (C ₁₅ H ₁₃ ON ₂ S)	205°	P+2-amino-4-methyl-B	207°	206°
<i>N</i> -Phenyl- <i>N'</i> -2-(5-methyl)-BD	<i>N</i> -Phenyl- <i>N'</i> -2-(5-methyl)-BC (C ₁₅ H ₁₃ ON ₂ S)	320°	P+2-amino-5-methyl-B	321°	321°
<i>N</i> -Phenyl- <i>N'</i> -2-(6-methyl)-BD	<i>N</i> -Phenyl- <i>N'</i> -2-(6-methyl)-BC (C ₁₅ H ₁₃ ON ₂ S)	315°	P+2-amino-6-methyl-B	315°	315°
<i>N</i> -Phenyl- <i>N'</i> -2-(6-ethoxy)-BD	<i>N</i> -Phenyl- <i>N'</i> -2-(6-ethoxy)-BC (C ₁₈ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₂ S)	235°	P+2-amino-6-ethoxy-B	235°	235°
<i>N</i> - <i>o</i> -Tolyl- <i>N'</i> -2-(4-methyl)-BD	<i>N</i> - <i>o</i> -Tolyl- <i>N'</i> -2-(4-methyl)-BC (C ₁₆ H ₁₃ ON ₂ S)	258°	(i) <i>o</i> -Tolylcarbamide + 4-methyl-2-amino-B (ii) <i>N</i> -2-(4-methyl)-BC + <i>o</i> -toluidine	260° 260°	260° 260°
<i>N</i> - <i>m</i> -Tolyl- <i>N'</i> -2-(5-methyl)-BD	<i>N</i> - <i>m</i> -Tolyl- <i>N'</i> -2-(5-methyl)-BC (C ₁₆ H ₁₃ ON ₂ S)	285°	(i) <i>m</i> -Tolylcarbamide + 5-methyl-2-amino-B (ii) <i>N</i> -2-(5-Methyl)-BC + <i>m</i> -toluidine	285° 284°	285° 284°
<i>N</i> - <i>p</i> -Tolyl- <i>N'</i> -2-(6-methyl)-BD	<i>N</i> - <i>p</i> -Tolyl- <i>N'</i> -2-(6-methyl)-BC (C ₁₆ H ₁₃ ON ₂ S)	272°	(i) <i>p</i> -Tolylcarbamide + 6-methyl-2-amino-B (ii) <i>N</i> -2-(6-Methyl)-BC + <i>p</i> -toluidine	273° 272°	273° 272°
<i>N</i> - <i>p</i> -Phenetyl- <i>N'</i> -2-(6-ethoxy)-BD	<i>N</i> - <i>p</i> -Phenetyl- <i>N'</i> -2-(6-ethoxy)-BC (C ₂₀ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₂ S)	237°	(i) <i>p</i> -Phenetidine + <i>N</i> -2-(6-ethoxy)-BC (ii) <i>p</i> -Phenetylcarbamide + 2-amino-6-ethoxy-B	237° 237°	237° 237°

BC represents benzothiazolylcarbamide
 BD " " carbodi-imide
 B represents benzothiazole
 P " phenyl isocyanate

* Sublimes.

The above carbamides were also obtained as follows :

(i). Phenyl isocyanate was treated in cold benzene separately with 4-methyl-, 5-methyl-, 6-methyl-, and 6-ethoxy-2-aminobenzothiazoles, affording *N*-2-(4-methyl-, 5-methyl-, 6-methyl-, and 6-ethoxy)-benzothiazolyl-*N'*-phenylcarbamide respectively. These were crystallised from glacial acetic acid and identified with the above mentioned compounds by their undepressed mixed m.p.

(ii). *N*-2-(4-methyl-, 5-methyl-, 6-methyl- and 6-ethoxy)-benzothiazolylcarbamides were first prepared by heating the relative 2-aminobenzothiazoles with an excess of carbamide at 155° for about 5 minutes (cf. this *Journal*, 1958, 35, 171). The unchanged urea and benzothiazoles were removed by washing with water and HCl (dilute). These carbamides were crystallised from acetic acid and melted at 300°, 310°, 308°, and 290° respectively. These were used in the preparation of *N*-aryl-*N'*-benzothiazolylcarbamides.

N-2-(4-Methyl)-benzothiazolyl-*N'*-*o*-tolyl-, *N*-2-(5-methyl)-benzothiazolyl-*N'*-*m*-tolyl-, *N*-2-(6-methyl)-benzothiazolyl-*N'*-*p*-tolyl-carbamides were prepared by heating the equimolecular quantities of the appropriate *N*-2-benzothiazolylcarbamide and amines at 160° for about 10 minutes. The solid product obtained was washed with HCl (dilute) and recrystallised from acetic acid. The melting points of the compounds and of their mixtures with the carbamides obtained from the hydrolysis of carbodi-imides are recorded in Table III.

(iii). The *N*-aryl-*N'*-2-benzothiazolylcarbamides were also prepared by heating the aryl (e.g., tolyl- and phenetyl-) carbamides with appropriate 2-aminobenzothiazoles at 160° for a few minutes. The carbamides were crystallised from acetic acid and were found identical with those obtained by procedure (ii) above.

N-Aryl-*N'*-2-benzothiazolylguanidines

Appropriate *N*-2-benzothiazolyl-*N'*-arylthiocarbamide (2 g.), yellow lead oxide (3 g.) and strong ethanolic ammonia (10-15 c.c.) were heated in a sealed tube for 3 to 4 hours at 90-100°. The alcoholic filtrate from the above reaction mixture gave crystals of *N*-aryl-*N'*-2-benzothiazolylguanidines. These were crystallised from absolute ethanol.

The guanidines, when treated in benzene or ether solution with hydrogen chloride, gave hydrochlorides, the equivalent weights of which were determined titrimetrically.

Picrates were obtained when ethanolic solutions of guanidines and picric acid were mixed. These were crystallised from absolute ethanol. The melting points of guanidines, their hydrochlorides and picrates and equivalent weight values and analytical values of nitrogen found are summarised in Table IV.

TABLE IV

† Thiocarbamide.	Guanidine.	M.P.	Found.	Calc.	Hydrochloride. M.P. Equiv.	Picrate. M.P.	
<i>N</i> -Phenyl- <i>N'</i> -2-BT	<i>N</i> -phenyl- <i>N'</i> -2-BG (C ₁₄ H ₁₂ N ₄ S)	154°	C: 62.9% H: 4.7 N: 21.0 S: 12.1	62.7% 4.5 20.9 11.9	203- 205°	305.1 (304.9)*	227°
<i>N</i> - <i>o</i> -Tolyl- <i>N'</i> -2-(4-methyl)-BT	<i>N</i> - <i>o</i> -Tolyl- <i>N'</i> -2-(4-methyl)- BG (C ₁₄ H ₁₆ N ₄ S)	170°	N: 18.8	19.0	217°	335.1 (332.5)	240°
<i>N</i> - <i>m</i> -Tolyl- <i>N'</i> -2-(5-methyl)- BT	<i>N</i> - <i>m</i> -Tolyl- <i>N'</i> -2-(5-methyl)- BG (C ₁₄ H ₁₆ N ₄ S)	195°	N: 18.4	19.0	196°	331.7 (332.5)	192°
<i>N</i> - <i>p</i> -Tolyl- <i>N'</i> -2-(6-methyl)-BT	<i>N</i> - <i>p</i> -Tolyl- <i>N'</i> -2-(6-methyl)- BG (C ₁₄ H ₁₆ N ₄ S)	198°	N: 19.2	19.0	196°	332.7 (332.5)	227°
<i>N</i> - <i>p</i> -Phenetyl- <i>N'</i> -2-(6-ethoxy)- BT	<i>N</i> - <i>p</i> -Phenetyl- <i>N'</i> -2-(6- (ethoxy)-BG (C ₁₈ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₄ S)	163°	N: 15.6	15.7	268°	395.7 (392.5)	238°
<i>N</i> -Phenyl- <i>N'</i> -2-(6-methyl)- BT	<i>N</i> -Phenyl- <i>N'</i> -2-(6-methyl)- BG (C ₁₄ H ₁₄ N ₄ S)	148°	N: 19.6	19.8	215°	320.3 (318.5)	213°

BT represents benzothiazolylthiocarbamide.

BG represents benzothiazolylguanidine.

† Desulphidised with PbO in presence of strong ammonia (alcoholic).

* Calculated values in parentheses.

Sincere thanks of the author are due to Dr. R. H. Sahasrabudhey for his interest, to Prof. G. B. Singh, Head of the Chemistry Department, and the authorities of the Banaras Hindu University for the facilities, and to the University Grants Commission for a scholarship.